

DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION OF LOW POWER PIPELINED FFT ARCHITECTURE FOR DSP APPLICATION

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ABSTRACT

The swift advancements in signal analysis applications have heightened the need for efficient, high-performance architectures to execute complex algorithms like the Quick Fourier Transform (FFT). This study introduces a VLSI implementation of a pipelined FFT architecture customized for DSP applications, addressing challenges in real-time processing, power consumption, and resource utilization. By exploiting the parallelism of the FFT algorithm and using pipelining techniques, our design achieves high throughput and low latency with minimal area overhead and power consumption. Implemented through VLSI techniques, this architecture can be integrated into dedicated DSP processors or system-on-chip (SoC) designs. It is optimized for area efficiency, making it suitable for resource-constrained applications while maintaining high performance. Extensive simulations and comparisons with existing FFT architectures demonstrate its superior throughput, latency, and power efficiency. Additionally, clock gating strategies are employed to further reduce power consumption. The design, synthesized using Xilinx tools and implemented on an Artix-7 FPGA board, was verified for theoretical accuracy using Verilog HDL.

Keywords: Fast Fourier Transform, Radix-2 Butterfly, Pipelining Technique, Clock Gating.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Specialized processors known as DSPs are meticulously designed microcontrollers engineered to execute the complex mathematical computations essential for real-time signal processing tasks [1]. They are essential in various applications, including telecommunications; audio and video analysis, radar technology, and medical signal processing. DSPs excel in performing operations such as filtering, Fast Fourier Transforms (FFTs), convolution, and signal compression with exceptional efficiency and speed [2]. These processors are characterized by their unique architectures, which support fast arithmetic operations, parallel processing, and low-latency data handling, making them adept at managing the continuous stream of data typical in real-time signal processing scenarios. DSPs incorporate features such as hardware multipliers, specialized instruction sets, and dedicated memory architectures to optimize performance for signal processing tasks. They are capable of executing multiple instructions per cycle and often include SIMD (Single Instruction, Multiple Data) and VLIW (Very Long Instruction Word) capabilities, which enhance their ability to handle large-scale computations and data throughput efficiently [3]. Additionally, DSPs are engineered with power-efficient modes and low-energy consumption features, making them vital for battery-operated and portable devices. Their programmability allows for flexibility in algorithm implementation, making them suitable for a variety of applications and adaptable to evolving technological needs. Furthermore, DSPs frequently support real-time operating systems and offer extensive peripheral interfaces for connecting with other hardware components, enabling seamless integration into larger systems. As a result, DSPs are fundamental to modern digital systems, providing the computational power and efficiency necessary to process and manipulate signals in a real-time environment [4].

Fig.1: Block diagram of DSP system

A) *Fast Fourier Transform:*

The Quick Fourier Transform (FFT) is a vital algorithm in signal analysis that efficiently computes the Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT) and its inverse, facilitating the transformation of signals between the time and frequency domains for easier analysis and manipulation. Implementing FFT using Very-Large-Scale Integration (VLSI) technology is essential for achieving the high-speed, low-power, and area-efficient processing required in modern electronic devices. By utilizing advanced VLSI techniques, Fast Fourier Transform architectures can be optimized to meet the demands of various applications, from communications to medical imaging, providing robust and efficient solutions for complex signal processing tasks [5].

$$X(k) = \sum_{m=0}^{M-1} x(m) \cdot W_M^{km} \quad (1)$$

$$W_n = e^{-i2\pi/M}$$

$$0 \leq k \leq M-1 \wedge 0 \leq m \leq M-1 \quad (2)$$

A. Radix-2:

The radix-2 method is a basic technique utilized for executing the Quick Fourier Transform (FFT) calculations. It efficiently breaks down a discrete Fourier transform (DFT) into smaller DFTs. This method decreases the computational overhead from $O(N^2)$ to $O(N \log N)$, where N represents the quantity of data points. This method repeatedly divides the input sequence into two halves, processing them recursively to achieve rapid and efficient transformation. Due to its straightforwardness and efficiency, the radix-2 FFT is widely employed in signal processing applications, enabling quick and efficient frequency domain analysis of signals [6].

II. BACKGROUND SURVEY

In [1] this method, present radix-2k feed-forward (MDC) FFT architectures that support any power-of-two parallel sample count and accommodate both Decimation in Time (DIT) and Frequency Decimation (DIF) decompositions. These designs achieve extremely high throughput with fewer hardware resources compared to parallel feedback architectures (MDF), making them perfect for challenging applications and opening new research avenues in feed-forward structures. The FFT, crucial for efficiently computing the DFT in signal processing, is implemented in hardware using pipelined architectures for high-performance, real-time processing with low area. Pipelined architectures, including feedback and feed-forward types, are essential for high-throughput applications like OFDM and UWB, addressing challenges such as FFT computation for multiple data sequences and parallel sample processing. This [2] work describes the implementation of FFT processors using two fused floating-point operations: a two-term dot product and an add-subtract unit. These fused operations optimize the "butterfly" computations in FFT, which involve complex multiplications, additions, and subtractions. Both radix-2 and radix-4 butterfly operations benefit from these fused operations, resulting in FFT processors that are approximately 15% faster and 30% smaller than traditional implementations using high-performance standard cell technology. Moreover, combining these methods provides slightly more precise numerical outcomes by minimizing rounding operations. In [3] this method Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT) has been replaced by the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) algorithm, which employs a divide-and-conquer principle to enhance computation speed by leveraging the symmetry of calculations for indices with even and odd values. a significant drawback remains in both FFT and DFT computations rely on complex multipliers that must handle changes in angle at every step due to twiddle factor multiplications, leading to increased hardware complexity, power consumption, and delay. In [4] this paper, we introduce a novel and efficient FFT algorithm designed for OFDM/DMT applications, along with its pipeline implementation outcomes. The proposed algorithm leverages the radix-4 butterfly unit, enabling it to process data at twice the speed of conventional algorithms. Moreover, the implementation is more area-efficient than traditional radix-4 algorithms because it reduces the number of nontrivial multipliers, similar to the radix-23 algorithm. The [5] advantages of employing digital convolution for implementing a specific pulse compression radar filter. Given the filter's bandwidth, a straightforward calculation of the necessary computation rate reveals that significant parallel processing would be required with existing integrated circuits. Various DFT computation methods are discussed, with the FFT algorithm being selected due to its regular structure and in-place computation, which facilitate parallel processing. The paper describes the parallelism in the radix-2 pipeline FFT, demonstrating that additional parallel processing is needed to achieve the desired processing rate. By computing n butterflies simultaneously at each stage of the FFT, a family of parallel pipeline FFT processors is developed.

III. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

In this study, a thorough design space is introduced exploration of various approximate multipliers, such as the Truncated Multiplier, to assess the potential energy savings and error metrics associated with approximate FFT hardware. By incorporating approximations in the multiplication and addition operations within the butterfly structure, Notable hardware simplifications result in decreases in circuit size, critical path length, and energy usage. Most multipliers and adders implement approximations by focusing on the least significant bits (LSB), allowing for controlled error incorporation in the decimal representation. These approximations are made by varying the operational precision based regarding the number of LSBs used, which typically results in minimal error magnitudes and facilitates higher maximum operating frequencies. Furthermore, to minimize power usage of the circuit, we have implemented clock control in our proposed design. This method can significantly decrease parameters such as power consumption and delay. Addressing power dissipation is a critical design concern in VLSI circuits. Our proposed work primarily focuses on dynamic power dissipation, which is minimized by reducing signal activity within the design. Because the clock network contributes significantly to power dissipation, substantial power savings can be achieved by gating the clock when it is unnecessary.

A. Approximate Multiplier and Adder:

Fig 2: (a) Approximate Multiplier

(b) Approximate Adder

B. Flip Flop based clock gating:

In many applications, latch based designs are moved to flip flop based designs. By splitting flip flop, we can see two latches from the master slave theorem. In this technique, we can see D flip flop with AND gate. Gated clock goes to high when flip-flop output and clock are in high state otherwise gated clock goes to zero state. That means when clock in sleep mode then gated clock also in zero state.

Fig.3: Clock gating using flip-flops

C. BLOCK DIAGRAM

Fig.4: 16 – point DIF FFT structure

Fig.5: FFT calculation by using radix-2 algorithm

V. EXPERIMENTAL RESULT AND DISCUSION

The experimental results for a 16-point FFT using the radix-2 algorithm were validated for theoretical accuracy with Verilog HDL. The design was implemented on an Artix-7 FPGA board using Xilinx tools, and a synthesized report was produced, detailing the area, power, and timing as shown in the first table, explained by Figure 8. The comparison between the proposed method and existing methods is illustrated in the second table, described by Figure9

Fig 6: Output of 16-point DIF FFT

FFT Calculation FFT Computation using Radix-2 DIF Algorithm	Ref [1] : FWM Design for FFT calculation	Proposed Work
Power	136mW	134mW
Critical path	42.79ns	36.66ns
LUTs and Slices	420 LUTs and 214 Slices	279 LUTs and 153 Slices

Fig 7: RTL Schematic of 16-point DIF FFT

Table I: Synthesis Result of Pipelined FFT Architecture

Pipelined FFT Architecture using Radix-2 DIF Algorithm	Pipelined Structure without Clock gating.	Pipelined Structure with Clock gating.
Dynamic Power	399mW	134mW
Static Power	167mW	141mW
Critical Path	36.66ns	36.66ns
LUTs and Slices	278 LUTs and 152 Slices	279 LUTs and 153 Slices

Fig.8: Bar graph of proposed DIF Radix-2 FFT Algorithm with or without clock gating.

Table II: COMPARISION OF RESULT WITH PROPOSED WORK

Fig.9: Bar graph comparison with proposed work and FWM design FFT calculation.

VI. CONCLUSION

This research suggests an innovative design for VLSI architectures of the Quick Fourier Transform (FFT) by leveraging arithmetic approximations. Compared to previous multiplier designs, this approach integrates an additional approximate multiplier, demonstrating enhanced efficiency for the radix-2 butterfly over its predecessors. This investigation comprehensively explores the synergetic integration of approximate multiplier architectures within the decimation-in-frequency (DIF) FFT butterfly, examining various levels of approximation in detail. Through extensive design space exploration, a group of approximate arithmetic configurations is elucidated, exhibiting a balanced tradeoff between design fidelity and energy efficiency. Finally, the results imply that prolonged multiplier, incorporating distinct approximation techniques, achieves substantial energy savings. The simulation outcomes, along with synthesis reports, have been meticulously analyzed, encompassing area and delay metrics obtained via Xilinx tools. Additionally, clock gating methods have been used to further reduce power consumption.

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